

Microfluidic generation of double layer hydrogel structures for the recapitulation of the hematopoietic stem cell niche

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Microfluidic device for the generation of double layer cell-laden beads. Left: Design layout and schematic of the operation of the microfluidic technology. Right: A. Double layer alginate beads extracted in several inner and outer layer sizes. Life/dead (B/C) staining of extracted alginate inner core beads containing human Mesenchymal Stem cells hMSCs after 4 hours at day 1.

Abstract

The use of adult stem cells, especially from bone marrow, in regenerative medicine has become increasingly important in the last years (1). Hematopoietic stem cells *in vivo* reside in a microenvironment known as a niche able to maintain them in a quiescent state, however alone cannot be expanded *in vitro*. Additionally to regulatory factors in these stem cell niches, a number of environmental and mechanical signals arising from the extracellular matrix are crucial regulators of stem cell fate (2). Micro-engineering a biomimetic three dimensional structure provides a realistic approach for studies of bone marrow stem cells, and further translational implementation. High-throughput microfluidics constitutes a promising technology, however, adaptation to accommodate adult stem cells in artificially fabricated niches remains still a challenge. In this work, a microfluidic-assisted double layer encapsulation device for the generation of cellular structures on demand is presented. Fine control of the structure geometry, composition and cell distribution in terms of size and shape can be achieved. In the presented droplet-based microdevice, hydrogel droplets are produced by hydrodynamic focusing techniques and gelled by the circulation of the droplet between two laminar flows, one containing the cross-linking agent. Droplet coating is achieved by synchronizing droplet production rates so that the gelled bead merges with the second layer droplet on its generation area, forming a double layered bead. Using this novel technology, layered hydrogel beads using both alginate and Puramatrix have been successfully generated for a range of sizes. The system was characterized and analysed for different operational conditions to optimize its efficiency. Cell viability was also demonstrated encapsulating human Mesenchymal Stem Cells hMSCs. The designed device constitutes a reliable and robust tool to generate double hydrogel concentric structures on demand and a realistic approach to build multi-layered cellular hydrogel beads to reproduce *in vitro* the compartmentalized microenvironment that exist *in vivo*. Moreover, the

presented generation technique uses only passive forces making the procedure especially suitable for the generation of cell constructs. This droplet-based niche mimicry strategy represents a promising technique able to provide optimal requirements for stem cell maintenance and further expansion for clinical applications and opens a wide field of potential applications within uTAS for tissue engineering applications.

Keywords: Microfluidics; microencapsulation; droplet technology; tissue engineering; stem cell niche.

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